

RESPONSE PATTERN OF MIXED BACTERIAL POPULATION TO ANTIMICROBIAL AGENTS.

Okoko, F.J. and Uwafili, N.P.
Department of Microbiology, Delta State University, Abraka.

ABSTRACT

The effect of four antimicrobial agents, Chloramphenicol, Tetracycline, Amoxicillin and Ciprofloxacin on the growth of *Staphylococcus aureus* and Salmonella species was studied. Tetracycline produced the highest inhibition for *Staphylococcus aureus* at a concentration of 0.0625mg/ml while Ciprofloxacin produced the highest inhibition for Salmonella species at a concentration of 0.2500mg/ml. Both bacteria isolates were susceptible to amoxicillin at the same minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) of 1.0000mg/ml. For combination thereby against individual isolates ciprofloxacin + Amoxicillin was inhibitory to *Staphylococcus aureus* at a concentration of 0.2500mg/ml which was the highest MIC. A combination of Tetracycline + Chloramphenicol was not inhibitory to Salmonella species. Combination therapy against mixed bacteria showed a MIC of 0.5000mg/ml for ciprofloxacin + Amoxicillin while Tetracycline + Chloramphenicol was not inhibitory. The result showed that Tetracycline and Ciprofloxacin are good antimicrobial agents for infections caused by *Staphylococcus aureus* and Salmonella respectively. For mixed bacterial infections cause by Staphylococcus and Salmonella species, ciprofloxacin and combination of Amoxicillin + Ciprofloxacin are effective.

KEY WORDS: Antimicrobial, inhibition, isolates, concentration, combination, population.

INTRODUCTION

Drugs have been used for the treatment of infectious diseases since the 17th century. However, chemotherapy as a science began with Paul Ehrlich in the first decades of the 20th century. Paul Ehrlich developed salvarsan which was the first documented example of a chemical used successfully as antimicrobial medication. He also formulated the principle of selective toxicity and recognized the specific chemical relationships between microbial pathogens and drugs; the development of drug resistance and the role of combined therapy.

The current era of antimicrobial chemotherapy began in 1935 with the discovery of the sulfanamides. In 1940, it was demonstrated that penicillin, which was discovered in 1929, could be an effective therapeutic drug (Hoht *et al* (1990). During the next 25years, research on chemotherapeutic agents largely centered on substances of microbial origin called antibiotics. The isolation, concentration, purification and mass production of penicillin were followed by the development of Streptomycin, Tetracycline, Chloramphenicol and other agents. The above agents were produced by mould species, *Streptomyces griseus*, soil Actinomycetes and *Streptomyces venezuelae* (Brook *et al* 2002).

ANTIMICROBIAL SUSCEPTIBILITY

Treatment of uncomplicated gastroenteritis caused by non typhoidal Salmonella is a matter of some contention. People with milder infection do not seek treatment and those who seek attention of physicians are usually quite ill and in great discomfort and expect antibiotic to relief their condition. However, Amoxicillin should be administered only to patients at risk for a poor outcome (Farthing *et al*, 1996).

Chloramphenicol is a substance produced originally from cultures of *Streptomyces venezuelae* but now manufactured synthetically. Chloramphenicol is rapidly absorbed from the gastrointestinal tract and widely distributed into those tissues and body fluids, excretion is mainly in the urine, 90% in inactive form. It is a potent inhibitor of protein synthesis in microorganisms. Chloramphenicol resistance is due to the distribution of the enzyme chloramphenicol acetyl transferase which is under plasmid control Moellering *et al* 2000.

Tetracyclines are a group of drugs that differ physically and in pharmacologic characteristics but have virtually identical antimicrobial properties and gives complete cross-resistance. All tetracyclines are readily absorbed from intestinal tracks and distributed widely in tissues but penetrate into the cerebro spinal fluid poorly. They inhibit the growth of all gram-positive and gram-negative bacteria but they do not inhibit fungi Brooks *et al* (2002).

Amoxicillin are members of the family penicillin which their side chains have been modified in the laboratory to create penicillin derivatives. They are broad spectrum penicillin which retains their activities against penicillin sensitive gram positive bacteria, yet they are also active against gram negative organisms. They can be inactivated by β -lactamases. (Nester *et al*, 2001).

Ciprofloxacin belong to the fluoroquinolones which are synthetic drugs which inhibit one or more of a group enzyme to poisons which maintain the supercoiling of a closed circular DNA with the bacterial cell.

The fluoroquinolones are bactericidal against a wide variety of bacteria including both gram-positive and gram-negative organisms.

TEST ORGANISMS

Staphylococcus aureus is a gram-positive spherical cell, usually arranged in grape-like irregular clusters. It grows rapidly on many types of media and is active metabolically, fermenting carbohydrates and producing pigments that vary from white to deep yellow Brooks *et al*, 2002. It is a normal flora of the skin and mucous membrane of humans. It is non-motile and does not cause a wide range of major and minor pathogenic infections. They can cause infections such as superficial inflammation, lesions with pus formation such as skin pustules, boils, carbuncles, phlebitis, styles, impetigo and pemphigus neonatonum.

Staphylococcus aureus rapidly develops antimicrobial resistance to many antimicrobial agents and present difficult therapeutic problems. Multiple drug resistance is explained by the acquisition of plasmid encoding for such resistance by *Staphylococcus aureus* strains. Certain strains of *S. aureus* are resistant and this occur more in hospital environments than in the community. (Baily and Scott, 1990).

SALMONELLA

Salmonella species are rod-shaped, motile, non-spore forming, gram-negative bacteria. They never ferment lactose or sucrose an form acid and sometimes gas from glucose and manose.

Environmental sources of salmonella include water, soil, animal feaces, raw meat, raw poultry, raw sea foods etc. they are transmitted from animals and animal products to humans where they cause enteritis, systemic infections and enteric fever. Acute symptom include nausea, vomiting, abdominal cramps, diarrhea, fever and headache. Salmonella carried by animals have been found to develop resistance to drugs such as tetracyclines incorporated into animal feeds while many species have been found to be sensitive to most antibiotics such as ceftriaxone, ciprofloxacin, afloxacin, levofloxacin, sparfloxacin, troxacin, ampillin, chloramphenicol etc, used in therapy (Brooks *et al*, 2002).

AIMS AND OBJECTIVES

This study is therefore designed to study the response pattern of mixed bacteria population to some selected antimicrobial agents and possible synergistic effects of these agents on the study organisms.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Pure isolates of *Staphylococcus aureus* and Salmonella species used for this study were obtained from Delta State University Health Center and were identified and characterized using cultural, morphological staining and biochemical properties as described by Buchanan and Gibbons (1974), Monica (1984) and Cowan and Steel (1974).

The identified microorganisms were transferred unto agar slants in sterilized bijou bottles and saved in the refrigerator for subsequent use.

The antimicrobial agents used for this study are Tetracycline hydrochloride B.P 250mg, produced by Yangahou No. 3 Pharmaceutical Company Limited, China. Chloramphenicol capsule, B.P. 250mg produced by Mendel Pharmaceutics PVI Limited, India, Ciprofloxacin tablets USP 500mg, produced by U.S International PVT Limited, India and Amoxicillin capsule B.P 500mg produced by Elder Pharmaceuticals Limited, Mumbere, India.

Five hundred milligrams of the different antimicrobial agents were dispensed into four different sterilized conical flasks. Five hundred milliliter of distilled water was added and the content of each flask was swirled gently to allow for the even distribution of the antimicrobial agents.

SUSCEPTIBILITY TEST

Ten milliliter of sterilized nutrient brought was dispensed into two sterilized test tubes, inoculated with 1ml *Salmonella* and *Staphylococcus aureus* respectively and were incubated at 237⁰C for 24h and observed for growth. The content of each tube was washed three times making use of a bench-top centrifuge (Gallenkamp Centrifuge, EEC) at 1400mg for 30min to remove all the media. Serial dilution to 10³ number of cells was made for each isolate.

Test on the susceptibility of the test microorganisms to the four antimicrobial agents was carried out using pour plate method.

One milliliter of each of the test organisms already diluted to 10³ was pipetted into sterile Petri dishes using 5ml sterile pipettes after which 1ml each from the stock solutions of the antimicrobial agents was added and mixed thoroughly. The plates for each antibiotics were prepared in duplicate. One and a half milliliter of sterile nutrient agar was dispensed into each Petri dish and their content swirled gently for proper mixing after which they were incubated at 37⁰C for 24h. The susceptibility of the test organisms was confirmed by the absence of growth on the inoculated plates. Sterile nutrient agar plates containing 1ml each of the test antibiotics were used as control.

DETERMINATION OF MINIMUM INHIBITORY CONCENTRATION (MIC)

Serial dilution was carried out on each of the antimicrobial agents making use of distilled water. Five sterile test tubes were used for each of the antimicrobial; agent and were placed in a test tube racks. Nine milliliter of distilled water was added into the first tube of each antimicrobial agent using well sterilized pipettes and labeled accordingly. One milliliter of the different antimicrobial agent was dispensed into each of the labeled test tubes and mixed thoroughly.

Serial dilution was made in decreasing concentration. One milliliter of the 10³ of each serially diluted test organisms was dispensed into separate sterile petri dishes for each antibiotic and labeled. One milliliter each of the antibiotic was added to the appropriate petri dish and mixed thoroughly after which nutrient agar was poured and plates were swirled for proper mixing. They were immediately incubate at 37⁰C for 24h and examined for visible growth. All experiments were in replicate. The least dilution for the antibiotic that yielded no growth is the minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC).

For the determination of MIC using two antimicrobial agents, 0.5ml each of the two antimicrobial agent was added to each of the petri dishes containing 1ml of the test organisms (*Salmonella* and *S. aureus*) was put in separate petri dish for the different test antibiotics and nutrient agar were poured. Each plate was mixed thoroughly and incubated at 37⁰C for 24h.

In determining the MIC using single therapy and mixed bacteria isolates, 0.5ml each of the test organisms (*Salmonella* and *S. aureus*) was put in separate petri dish for the different test antibiotics and nutrient agar were poured. Each plate was mixed thoroughly and incubated at 37⁰C for 24h.

The following were set-up as experimental control.

The Negative Controls are:

Nutrient broth only.

Nutrient + Sterile distilled water.

All test organisms + nutrient agar.

All test antibiotics + washed test organisms

Nutrient broth + sterile distilled water

Positive Control is: Nutrient agar + organisms

RESULTS

Table 1 shows the various concentration of the antibiotics used for this study. The effect of tetracycline, chloramphenicol, ciprofloxacin and amoxicillin on the growth of Salmonella species is shown in Table 2. ciprofloxacin and amoxicillin showed a minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) of 0.5000mg/ml and 1.000mg/ml respectively on the test organisms while the organisms are resistant to both tetracycline and chloramphenicol.

The effects of the antibiotics on *Staphylococcus aureus* was shown in Table 3. tetracycline had MIC of 0.0625mg/ml for the test organisms while ciprofloxacin and amoxicillin had MIC of 0.5000mg/ml and 1.0000mg respectively for the same organism, *Staphylococcus aureus* was totally resistant to chloramphenicol.

The effects of combined therapy on the test organisms was shown in Table 4 and 5. The MIC for the combination of Tetracycline and chloramphenicol on *Staphylococcus aureus* was 1.000mg/ml while that of ciprofloxacin and amoxicillin with a MIC of 0.5000mg/ml as shown in Table 5.

The effects of single therapy on the mixed bacteria specimen is shown in Table 6. A mixture of *Staphylococcus aureus* and Salmonella species were resistant to both tetracycline and chloramphenicol but inhibited by ciprofloxacin and amoxicillin with MIC of 0.5000mg/ml and 1.000mg/ml respectively.

The effects of combined therapy on the growth of mixed bacteria specimen is shown on Table 7. The test organisms (*Staphylococcus aureus* Salmonella species) were resistant to the combination of tetracycline and chloramphenicol while they were inhibited by the combination of ciprofloxacin and amoxicillin at MIC 0.5000mg/ml.

Table 1: Serial Dilution of Antimicrobial Agents

ANTIMICROBIAL AGENTS	CONCENTRATION Mg/ml				
	Tetracycline	1.0000	0.5000	0.2500	0.1250
Chloramphenicol	1.0000	0.5000	0.2500	0.1250	0.0625
Ciprofloxacin	1.0000	0.5000	0.2500	0.1250	0.0625
Amoxicillin	1.0000	0.5000	0.2500	0.1250	0.0625

Table 2: Effect of the four Antimicrobial Agents on the growth of *Salmonella Species*

Concentration Mg/ml	Growth of Test Organism after 24h			
	TET	CHL	CIP	AMO
1.0000	++	+	-	⊗
0.5000	++	++	-	+
0.2500	++	++	⊗	++
0.1250	++	++	+	++
0.0625	++	++	++	++

KEY

++ Heavy growth, + Light growth, - No growth, Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC)
 ⊗T: Tetracycline, CHL: Chloramphenicol, CIP: Ciprofloxacin, AMO: Amoxicillin

Table 3: Effect of the four Antimicrobial Agents on the growth of *Staphylococcus aureus*

Concentration Mg/ml	Growth of Test Organism after 24h			
	TET	CHL	CIP	⊗AMO
1.0000	-	+	-	⊗
0.5000	-	+	⊗	+
0.2500	-	+	+	+
0.1250	-	++	++	++
0.0625	⊗	++	++	++

KEY

++ Heavy growth, + Light growth, - No growth, Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC)
 ⊗T: Tetracycline, CHL: Chloramphenicol, CIP: Ciprofloxacin, AMO: Amoxicillin

Table 4: Effect of Combined therapy on the growth of *Staphylococcus aureus*

Concentration Mg/ml	Growth of Test Organism after 24h	
	TET+ CHL	CIP + AMO ⊗
1.0000	⊗	-
0.5000	+	-
0.2500	+	⊗
0.1250	+	+
0.0625	+	+

KEY

++ Heavy growth, + Light growth, - No growth, Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC)
 ⊗T: Tetracycline, CHL: Chloramphenicol, CIP: Ciprofloxacin, AMO: Amoxicillin

Table 5: Effect of Combined therapy on the growth of *Salmonella species*

Concentration Mg/ml	Growth of Test Organism after 24h	
	TET+ CHL	CIP + AMO
1.0000	+	-
0.5000	+	⊗
0.2500	++	+
0.1250	++	+
0.0625	++	+

KEY

++ Heavy growth, + Light growth, - No growth, Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC)
 ⊗T: Tetracycline, CHL: Chloramphenicol, CIP: Ciprofloxacin, AMO: Amoxicillin

Table 6: Effect of Single therapy on the growth of mixed bacteria (*Salmonella species* + *Staphylococcus aureus*)

Concentration Mg/ml	Growth of Test Organism after 24h			
	TET	CHL	CIP	⊗/MO
1.0000	+	+	-	⊗
0.5000	+	+	⊗	+
0.2500	+	+	+	+
0.1250	+	+	++	+
0.0625	+	+	++	+

KEY

++ Heavy growth, + Light growth, - No growth, Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC)
 ⊗T: Tetracycline, CHL: Chloramphenicol, CIP: Ciprofloxacin, AMO: Amoxicillin

Table 7: Effect of Combine therapy on the growth of mixed bacteria (*Salmonella species* + *Staphylococcus aureus*)

Concentration Mg/ml	Growth of Test Organism after 24h	
	TET+ CHL	CIP + AMO
1.0000	+	-
0.5000	+	⊗
0.2500	++	+
0.1250	++	++
0.0625	++	++

KEY

++ Heavy growth, + Light growth, - No growth, Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC)
 ⊗T: Tetracycline, CHL: Chloramphenicol, CIP: Ciprofloxacin, AMO: Amoxicillin

DISCUSSION

Gram-positive bacteria are usually more sensitive to antibiotics than gram-negative bacteria, although some antibiotics act only on gram-negative bacteria (Thomas, 1979)

From the results obtained in this study, it could be seen that *Staphylococcus aureus* a gram-negative organism, was sensitive to three of the four test antimicrobial agents used for this study: tetracycline, ciprofloxacin and amoxicillin. *Salmonella species* which is a gram-negative organisms was sensitive to only two of the four antimicrobial agents namely ciprofloxacin and amoxicillin. Both organisms were found to be resistant to chloramphenicol. The development of resistance to antimicrobial agents by organisms may be due to misuse of drugs, use of drugs in life stock fees; the veterinary use of microbial agents may select resistant organisms and facilitate their spread.

Resistance of microorganisms to antibiotics may be mediated by chromosomally located genes by horizontal transfer through plasmids and transposons. Many of the resistant genes present as plasmids and transposons of gram-negative bacteria are integrated in integrons. Class 1 integrons are wide spread among *Salmonella species*.

The rates of resistance of salmonella species to tetracycline, chloramphenicol, ampicillin and trimethoprim-sulfamethoxazole increased drastically between 1984 to 2001. the susceptibility of the two bacteria isolates to ciprofloxacin is because ciprofloxacin blocks the action of bacteria enzyme catalyzing the transpeptidation reaction during cell wall synthesis in prokaryotes. *Staphylococcus aureus* is susceptible to tetracycline because tetracycline inhibits synthesis in the organisms by combining with the 30S subunits of the ribosome and inhibiting of tRNA molecule to the ribosome.

Treatment with antimicrobial combinations may be necessary in certain cases. The administration of two or more agents may be beneficial in the following situations:

- To treat mixed bacteria infections in which the organisms are not susceptible to a common agent.
- To achieve a synergistic antimicrobial activity against particularly resistant strains.
- To overcome bacterial tolerance
- To prevent the emergence of drug resistance
- To minimize toxicity and
- To prevent inactivation of an antibiotic by enzymes produced by other bacteria that are present.

Ideally, antimicrobial selection should be based on different mechanisms of actions and on spectra of activity that are complementary. β -lactams are often selected because their actions is unique and not only complement other drugs but also facilitates their movement through the damaged cell wall into the microbe. Examples of combination therapy for mixed infections include the use of clindamycin metronidazole or the semi synthetic penicillin in combination with amino glycosides for their efficacy on gram-negative organisms. Preventing of development of resistance with combination of antimicrobial therapy is best exemplified by the use of carbonicillin or amikacin together with gentamycin or tobramycin for the treatment of Pseudomonas and other related infections.

CONCLUSION

Since many infectious microorganism have apparently developed resistance to many of the existing antimicrobial agents, it is important that more effort be directed towards research on the development of more efficacious antimicrobial agents which working singly or in combination would help check the threat of these microorganisms to human existence.

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Correspondence Author

Okoko, F.J.

Department of Microbiology, Delta State University, Abraka.